

The relationship between digitalization, sustainability and resilience in supply chain: A literature review

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Abstract

Purpose: The goal is to explore and map the prevailing supply chain practices from two perspectives, a) the integration between sustainability and resilience concepts, and b) the integration between digitalization, sustainability, and resilience in the supply chain (SC).

Methodology: A sequential procedure has been followed in the structure of the literature review as displayed in the table- 1.

Table-1: The sequential steps of literature review process

Step-1: Selection of main dimensions
Step-2: Selection of synonyms of keywords
Step-3: Search String used in Scopus
Step-4: Assess the quality of the journals based on the presence in Scimago journal and country ranking (SJR)
Step-5: Considered articles belonging only Q1 and Q2
Step-6: Consider articles belonging only to Gold Star, Gold and Silver ranking of management engineering list of Italian Association of Management Engineering (AiIG), March 2022
Step-7: Individual Title and abstract reading and assessment of these selected articles
Step-8: Final number of articles based on the above criteria for full reading and clustering

The sequential procedure ended to the selection of 61 articles from Scopus database. The Prisma diagram (Asante et al., 2021) and Vos-viewer is used for visualization of the connection between literatures. The following figure is the conceptual framework.

Figure 1: The conceptual framework of the study

Findings: The 61 papers have been clustered from various perspectives: theoretical lens, technological application, scopes and geographical area. The identified practices have been categorized into different dimensions. It is evident that collaboration as resilience is intently integrated with social sustainability. Moreover, agility and flexibility has strong association with workers and management as social sustainability (Jena & Ghadge, 2021). Visibility through tracking-tracing ensure knowledge management, social audit and environmental sustainability (Sauer et al., 2022). Besides several studies confirm that resilient SC practices can have impact on social and environmental sustainability but there is also reverse finding (Eggert & Hartmann, 2022). Digitalization in visible supplier orientation, product reconfiguration and operations is supportive for sustainability (Bag et al., 2021). Besides, digitalization ensure resilient SC by reducing energy consumption and green distribution channel (Dev et al., 2021).

Practical implications: Academia, industry partners, and policy makers can benefit from the finding of structured analysis of the integrated SC practices.

Contribution: This paper is a comprehensive literature review for the relationship between digitalization, sustainability and resilience. We showed the integration in general, digest prevailing challenges, and point out potential research gaps.

Keywords: Sustainability, Resilience, Digitalization

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